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Synthesis, spectral characterization and antibacterial activity of novel Schiff base ligand derived from curcumin

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to synthesis a ligand with biological activity, The ligand examined in this study was designated as [(1E,5Z,6E)-5-((2-(1H-benzo[d]imidazol-2-yl) phenyl) imino)-1,7-bis(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)hepta-1,6-dien-3-one)] was synthesised through a reaction involving a molar ratio of 1:1 between curcumin: 2-(1H-benzo[d]imidazol-2yl) aniline. The reaction medium utilized was methanol, with glacial acetic acid (GAA) serving as the catalyst. The reactants were refluxed for a duration of 6 hours, maintaining the constant temperature of 70 0C. Various techniques, including ultra-infrared (FT-IR), molar conductivity, 1H and 13C- NMR, magnetic susceptibility and UV-Visible, were employed to identify the resulting compounds in this research. The complexes were synthesised with reaction of a molar Ratio 2:1 (Ligand: metal salt), the compound was identified as a bi-dentate ligand capable of coordinating through both the azomethane group (CN) and the carbonyl group (C=O). Following the assessment of antibacterial activity of the compounds against four bacteria strains (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*), it was determined that both the ligand and its metal complexes (Co^{+2} , Cr^{+3} and Cu^{+2}) exhibited positive results.

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Introduction

The remarkable benzimidazole nucleus exhibits a wide range of biological and medicinal properties. The significance of the heterocyclic structure of benzimidazole has been broadened to include a diverse array of bioactive properties, including antibacterial, antifungal, anti-inflammatory, anthelmintic, anti-tubercular, anti-thrombotic; anti-platelet and anticoagulant, anti-ulcer, anti-protozoal, antiviral (Lotfi et al. 2020).

It was indicated that benzimidazole targets included anti-hypertensive, strong non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors, hepatitis C virus inhibitors, anticonvulsants, ulcerogenic compounds, nonpeptide angiotensin II receptor antagonists, strong activators of AMP-activated protein kinase, and anti-leukemic agents. The benzimidazole core has been shown to effectively

treat tuberculosis Bhati et al (2020). Benzimidazole found to have an extensive applications as a ligand it contributed significantly in coordination chemistry development (Alminderej et al., 2021).

It was also found that the complexes synthesized using benzimidazole as ligand has a exhibited a wide range of biological activities such as, antidiabetic activity against α -amylase, antibacterial, and antifungal, properties, antioxidant activity against DPPH, protein tyrosine phosphate inhibition, and significant antimalarial effects. Additionally, a Schiff base derived from 2- (1H-benzimidazol-2-yl)aniline, was identified as a crucial precursor that enabled the synthesis of various metal complexes with promising applications in medicine, particularly in antibacterial treatments (Lotfi et al. 2020; Sandhu et al. 2023).

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Schiff bases are considered to be one of the bioactive substances. The free ligand exhibits a lower biological impact when compared to their metal complexes (Najem et al., 2022). β -diketones Schiff base ligands played an important role in the development in the coordination chemistry and biological system (Naureen et al. 2021). The metal complexes synthesized from β -diketones Schiff base ligands can be ascribed to chelation, which markedly alters the physicochemical characteristics of the ligand.

Chelation theory posits that the development of a coordination complex diminishes the polarity of the metal ion by partially sharing its positive charge with the ligand's donor atoms, such as nitrogen and oxygen. This increased delocalization of electron density enhances the lipophilicity of the complex, which in turn facilitates better penetration through lipid membranes of microbial cells, improving bioavailability and biological action. Additionally, complexation may interfere with microbial enzyme systems or alter cellular metabolism more effectively than the free ligand (Chohan et al., 2006).

Curcumin, found in turmeric, a yellow spice, and exhibited antioxidant properties along with analgesic and anticancer effects (Najem et al., 2022; Ali et al. 2013). Several investigations into curcumin have employed the ionic structure in scenarios where keto-enol equilibrium existed or when the compound was fully ketogenic, yielding varied outcomes. Curcumin could be beneficial in addressing overload chelation and mineral toxicity. Due to its recognized strong chelating properties with various metal ions. A specific type of curcumin was referred to as keto-enol (Prasad et al., 2021; Ali et al. 2021).

Benzimidazole is an attractive chemical for integration due to its proven bioactivity and ability to form strong connections with biological targets. Therefore, designing a Schiff base that combines curcumin and benzimidazole creates a hybrid molecule with potentially enhanced pharmacological properties. The resulting ligand not only retains the beneficial features of both parent compounds but also introduces new metal-binding sites, making it a promising candidate for coordination chemistry and biomedical applications (Rauf et al. 2018; Keri et al. 2015).

Materials and Methods

All chemicals and reagents used in this study were purchased from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany) and Fluka (Buchs, Switzerland).

Synthesis of schiff base ligand HL¹

Methanol (10 ml) was utilized to dissolve curcumin (0.368 g, 1 mmol), followed by a drop wise addition of 2-(1H-benzo[d]imidazol-2-yl) aniline (0.209 g, 1mmol) that was dissolved in 5ml of methanol.

The reactant mixture was refluxed for 6 hours in the presence of the catalyst GAA at a fixed temperature of 70 °C, the reaction was carried under inert atmosphere. Following this, it was filtered to remove unreacted materials. The brown precipitate collected was washed and recrystallized using hot methanol. The resulting crystals exhibited a brown with melting point 176 °C.

The acquired results and the elemental analyses confirmed the structure of the synthesized ligand. FT-IR, ¹H-NMR and ¹³C-NMR. HL1: ((1E,5Z,6E)-5-((2-(1H-benzo[d]imidazol-2-yl) phenyl) imino)-1,7-bis(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)hepta-1,6-dien-3-one).

Yield: 65%, elemental analysis results indicated the following compositions: Carbon (C) at 72.97%, Hydrogen (H) at 5.22%, Nitrogen (N) at 7.51%, and Oxygen (O) at 14.29%. Identified: C, 72.1; H, 5.15; N, 7.30. ¹H NMR δ /ppm: 9.2 (OH), 12.4 (s, NH), 7.29-7.6 (m, 12H aromatic), 3.5 (s, CH₃); ¹³C NMR δ /ppm: 152.69 and 161.65 (C=N), 55.9 (OCH₃) 126.81-147.91 (C aromatic), 41.15 (CH₂); FT-IR (cm⁻¹) 3470 ν (O-H), 1614 ν (C=N), 1670 ν (C=O), 1273 ν (-CO phenolic), 1024 ν (-OCH₃); UV-Vis. (λ_{max} , nm): 288, 423 ($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$), (n $\rightarrow \pi^*$). The synthesis process of the ligand has been illustrated in figure 1.

Fig. 1. Synthesis route for the ligand (HL)

Synthesis of metal complexes

The transition metals complexes of CrCl₃·6H₂O, CoCl₂·6H₂O and CuCl₂·2H₂O were synthesized. The synthesis process was conducted with a reaction ratio of 1:2, [(0.237 of CoCl₂·6H₂O, 0.170 gm of CuCl₂·2H₂O and 0.266 gm of CrCl₃·6H₂O): 1.118 gm of ligand] were used in the reaction involving refluxing the reaction mixture at a constant temperature of 60 °C for 6 hours, utilizing KOH as a base while using GAA as the catalyst and methanol 5 ml as a solvent. Subsequently, it underwent

filtration and was washed with hot methanol to eliminate any residual reactants. The synthesis process of the metal complexes has been illustrated in figure 2.

Fig. 2. Synthesis route for the metal complexes

Estimation of Biological Activity

The compounds biological activity was assessed utilizing the agar-diffusion technique (Abdelwahed et al. 2025), comparing it to the IZ of a common antibiotic (Ceftriaxone) against two G-positive and two G-negative bacterial species namely *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC 27853), *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 25923) and *Bacillus subtilis* (ATCC 6633) respectively. All bacterial taxa were provided kindly by Prof. Juman Khaleel Al-Sabbagh (Microbiology Department, College of Veterinary Medicine, University of Kerbala, Iraq). The selected bacteria exhibited significant resistance to pharmaceutical compounds.

Results and Discussion

The ligand synthesized underwent characterization through FT-IR, UV-Visible, H1,13C-NMR analyses, with the results explained below. The ratio of metal salts to Schiff base utilized in the synthesis of the complexes was 1:2 moles (metal salts: ligand). The reaction produced solid and colored complexes.

The analytical results presented in table 1 aligned with the proposed formula for the molar ratio of metal to Schiff base. The complexes exhibited partial solubility in solvents such as water, methanol, ethanol and chloroform, whereas all compounds demonstrated complete dimethylformamide and dimethyl sulfoxide. Table 1 displayed a few of the chemical and physical properties.

Table 1 Characteristics of the ligand and its metal complexes

Compounds	M.Wt	M.P	Color	Yield%
HL(C ₃₄ H ₂₉ N ₃ O ₅)	559	176	Orange	65
[Co(HL) ₂ Cl ₂]	1248	286	Brown	70
[Cu(HL) ₂ Cl ₂]	1252.5	281	Brown	81
[Cr(HL) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	1241	294	Dark green	68

*Molecular weight (M.Wt), Melting point (M.P)

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy

The FT-IR spectroscopy demonstrated a peak at 1624 cm⁻¹, indicating the formation of the C=N group, which serve as evidence for the ligand's formation. Additionally, a peak at 1670 cm⁻¹ belonged to the carbonyl group. The peak corresponding to -OCH₃ was observed at 1024 cm⁻¹. Figure 1 illustrated the FT-IR chart of the ligand (Al-Qazzaz et al. 2020; Ali et al. 2021; Danilescu et al. 2021).

The FT-IR spectrum of the metal complexes indicated a shift in the azomethane group, along with the shift in the peak of the carbonyl group. This shift, ranging from 1602 to 1618 cm⁻¹, confirmed that both the imine and the carbonyl group were coordinated with the metal ion (Saritha et al. 2021; Liao et al. 2021). Another indication of the coordination process was the emergence of a new bond in the range of 230-250 cm⁻¹, which indicated the M-Cl bond. Additionally, a new bond has formed in the range 420-450 cm⁻¹, representing the stretching frequencies of the Metal-Nitrogen (M-N) bond (Najem et al 2022, Kheirkhahi et al. 2023). Table 2 listed the data collected.

Fig. 3. Fourier Transform Infrared spectrum of the ligand.

Table 2 The data collected from FTR

Compounds	C=N	NH	C=O	M-N	M-Cl
HL ¹ (C ₃₄ H ₂₉ N ₃ O ₅)	1624	3441	1670	-----	----
[Co(HL ¹) ₂ Cl ₂]	1600	3410	1655	433	250
[Cr(HL ²) ₂ Cl ₂]	1616	3414	1660	446	240
[Cu(HL ¹) ₂ Cl ₂]	1620	3414	1620	439	245

UV-Visible spectroscopy

The spectra of the ligand displayed a band at 247nm attributed to the $n \rightarrow \pi$ transition, along with another band at 350nm associated with the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ (Ahmed et al. 2013; Ali et al. 2021).

In addition to the intra-ligand field, the spectrum of the complexes displayed the d-d transition as follows: the copper complex exhibited a band at 760nm due to the ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{2g}$, while the Cr(III) complex presented a band at 773nm resulting from the ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (f) transition. The Co(II) complex exhibited a band at 779 nm as a result of the ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ transition. The collected data validated that all three complexes exhibited an octahedral geometry (Chandra et al. 2009; Najem et al. 2022).

Table 3 along with figures 4 and 5 showed the UV-Visible spectrum and the data collected.

Table 3 UV-Visible spectrum data of the synthesized compound

Compound	λ (nm)	ϵ_{\max} (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	Transition	Assignments
HL	247	171.7	$n \rightarrow \pi$	-----
	350	119.3	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	
[Co (HL) ₂ Cl ₂]	246	1552	$n \rightarrow \pi$	octahedral
	345	1766	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	
	379	6	${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$	
[Cr (HL) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	348	1235	$n \rightarrow \pi$	octahedral
	351	2061	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	
	773	4	${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (F)	
[Cu (HL) ₂ Cl ₂]	246	1365	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	octahedral
	344	865	$n \rightarrow \pi^*$	
	760	3	${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{2g}$	

Fig. 4. The UV-visible spectrum of the ligand.

Fig. 5. The UV-Visible spectrum of the ligand.

Mass Spectroscopy

The mass spectroscopy analysis of the ligand revealed a distinct peak that indicated the molecular ion at $m/z = 559$ amu, corresponding to $(m+1)$ of the Schiff base ligand with the formula $(C_{34}H_{29}N_3O_5)$. The ligand spectrum exhibited a series of peaks at $m/z=434$, 411, 294, 256, 219, 94, 71 amu, respectively.

The strength of the peak indicated the fragments stability. The mass fragmentation of the ligand has been depicted in Figure 6; while the spectra was illustrated in figure 7.

Fig. 6. Suggested mass fragmentation of the ligand.

Fig. 7. Mass spectrum of the ligand

1H -NMR and ^{13}C -NMR spectroscopy-

The NMR spectrum of the ligand was obtained to determine the compounds' structure, with the spectra recorded in DMSO- d_6 and TMS served as a standard. 1H -NMR spectra displayed numerous signals, indicating the presence of various groups within the ligand. The signals were interpreted as follows: A single signal was observed at 9.8 ppm, indicating the presence of the OH group. Another single signal appeared at 10.4 ppm, representing the NH group. Additionally, multiple signals were detected in the range of 7.26-7.55 ppm, indicating the Aromatic ^{13}C -NMR spectrum revealed many signals, especially: 150.69 (C=N), 126.86-137.91 (Aromatic) and 41.15 (CH_2) (Hussien et al 2018; Ahmed et al. 2014; Naeimi et al 2013). The data of 1H -NMR & ^{13}C -NMR that was collected are listed in table 4.

Table 4 $^1\text{H-NMR}$ & $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ data of the ligand.

HL			
Functional group	$^1\text{H-NMR}$	Functional group	$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$
$\text{H}_{\text{aromatic}}$	7.26-7.55	$\text{C}=\text{N}$	150.69
OH	9.8	$\text{C}_{\text{aromatic}}$	126.86-137.91
NH	10.4	41.15	41.15

Estimation of Biological Activity

The compounds biological activity was assessed utilizing the agar-diffusion technique, comparing it to the IZ of a common antibiotic (Ceftriaxone) against two G-positive and two G-negative bacterial species: *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. aureus*, and *B. subtilis* respectively. The selected bacteria exhibited significant resistance to pharmaceutical compounds.

The disparity in antibacterial efficacy may be examined utilizing chelation theory and the overtones model. The chelation theory posits that the metal ion inside a chelate complex might augment the stability and bioavailability of the metal, hence possibly increasing its efficacy in biological interactions. This is particularly pertinent in antimicrobial research, as metal complexes with chelating agents frequently exhibit heightened efficacy against microbes due to improved cell membrane penetration (Najem et al. 2022; Mohammed et al. 2024). A study by Zhang and his co-authors was investigated the role of metal chelation in augmenting antimicrobial activity, revealing that metal ions, especially Cu^{2+} , associated with chelating agents exhibited enhanced efficacy in inhibiting *E. coli* growth due to the increased stability and bioavailability of the metal (Zhang et al., 2017)

Overtone's theory asserts that the permeability of a cell membrane is influenced by the lipophilicity of the material. The more lipophilic a complex is, the easier it can cross the lipid-rich membrane of microorganisms. For example, Cu^{2+} complexes, when coordinated with lipophilic ligands, may show enhanced antibacterial activity by facilitating easier penetration into the bacterial cell membrane, which is largely hydrophobic (Rauf et al., 2018).

The chelation hypothesis explained the ability of the compounds to move through the organism's cell membrane. The positive charge was partially shared between the donor group and the metal, leading to the decrease in a polarity of the metal ion. Consequently, this enhanced the lipophilic property, enabling the metal complex to get through the lipid bilayer of the cell more effectively the compound might undergo decomposition in

the cell medium (Mohammed et al., 2024). Figure 8 illustrate bioactivity chart for the synthesized compounds.

Fig. 8. Bioactivity chart for the synthesized compounds.

Conclusion

The Schiff base ligand examined in this study was synthesized through the reaction of Curcumin and 2-(1H-benzo[d]imidazol-2-yl) aniline (HL). The Nitrogen atom in the imine group participated in the coordination process as a dentate, while the oxygen of the carbonyl group also contributed to the coordination. The data collected indicated that all the complexes synthesized in the research exhibited an octahedral structural form.

All of the compounds demonstrated biological efficiency against four distinct species of bacteria, and the synthesized compounds exhibited adequate inhibition across a range of values against the bacterial strains. Future studies may explore the pharmacological potential of these metal complexes, along with their mechanism of interaction with DNA or enzymes.

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Ethical Approval

N/A

Conflict of Interest

The author declare no conflict of interest.

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